

Examine the Connection between Poverty and Crime in Oliver Twist

Mr. Prakaash AU

Assistant Professor, Department of English, Aditya Arts and Science College, Coimbatore

(Affiliated to Bharathiar University, Coimbatore)

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Abstract

This study explores the intricate relationship between poverty and crime as depicted in *Oliver Twist* (1838) by Charles Dickens. Elevated unemployment, limited educational opportunities, and disrupted family structures contribute to widespread poverty, which, in turn, fuels criminal activities. Dickens presents poverty as a critical social and economic issue in 19th-century England, reflecting the harsh realities of the time through his own experiences. The novel portrays how the system punishes Oliver and other orphans for the “crime” of being born poor, highlighting the absence of social mobility. Through characters like Noah Claypole and Charley Bates, Dickens illustrates how a lack of education and opportunity emphasize the cycle of poverty and criminal behaviour. This analysis underscores the novel’s role as a social critique, revealing the consequences of systemic neglect and economic disparity.

Keywords: *Poverty, Crime, Charles Dickens, Social critique, 19th-century England, Education, Economic disparity*

Introduction

Oliver Twist or *The Parish Boy’s Progress* by Charles Dickens portrays the dangerous path of the main character, Oliver, from the poverty of the workhouse to the murkier world of crime, eloquently capturing the brutal reality of 19th-century London. The story reveals a world in which going from begging for basic necessities to committing crimes like burglary is sparked by poverty. The workhouse, which is representative of Dickens’ criticism of the Poor Laws and the dehumanising circumstances endured by the poor, is where Oliver is first exposed to misery. Under this sense, the begging bowls represent the struggle for survival under a system that disregards the needs of the underprivileged.

The impact of Workhouses and Social Policies

Oliver gets caught up with Fagin’s group of young criminals as he breaks out of the workhouse and explores the shadowy side of London. Fagin is a cunning character who takes advantage of the poor kids’ weakness and leads them to a life of crime. Oliver’s transformation from a frantic cry for survival to active involvement in illegal activities is symbolised by the shift from begging bowls to burglaries. Dickens skilfully depicts how people, like Oliver, turn to crime as a method of survival when they lack social support and economic opportunities. Oliver’s moral struggle in this paradigm highlights ethical questions about a culture that marginalises individuals and emphasises the link between poverty, criminality and societal negligence.

Literature Review

The motif of burglaries in *Oliver Twist* symbolizes the extreme measures individuals may resort to when pushed to the brink by poverty. The criminal activities of characters like the Artful Dodger and Oliver himself become a manifestation of the systemic failures that perpetuate a cycle of poverty-driven crime. Dickens masterfully weaves a narrative that challenges readers to confront the societal structures that drive individuals to such desperate measures. The novel stands as a timeless critique

of social injustice and economic disparities, urging readers to reflect on the consequences of a society that neglects its most vulnerable members, pushing them from begging bowls to the shadowy realm of burglaries.

Analysing Dickens' Social Critique

The boy called Oliver Twist grew up as a communal orphan in a workhouse. He was born to an unknown, poor and tattered woman who died immediately after the childbirth. Oliver spent several years in the workhouse together with other children – orphans in a similar situation. When he was nine years old, a municipal deputy Mr. Bumble, the beadle, reached an agreement with a head of the workhouse that it was a high time Oliver started working. So, he was placed at Mr. Sowerberry's, the gravedigger, to be apprenticed. Oliver found a friend in Mr. Sowerberry personally, however the other members of the household bullied him and they caused harm to him, therefore one day early in the morning Oliver escaped with an intention to get into London which meant a symbol of hope and a new beginning to him. During the journey Oliver met a boy of about the same age. His name was Jack Dawkins, however more often he was called with a nickname – the "Artful Dodger". Oliver followed Jack Dawkins up to London to the place where he lived together with a few other boys at an old Jewish man's called Fagin. At the dwelling of Mr. Fagin Oliver in the course of time met other friends and co-workers of his, for example an adult man called Bill Sikes or two young girls Nancy and Betsy. Oliver had not recognized that those people actually formed a thieving gang until he went on an expedition with them and he was arrested for the theft of Mr. Brownlow's handkerchief, which in reality he did not commit. Fortunately, the truth transpired, Mr. Brownlow even took charge of frightened and wretched Oliver and he looked after him in his house.

The Factors Contributing to Poverty and Criminality

However, when Oliver was running an errand for Mr. Brownlow, he was kidnapped by Nancy and he got to Fagin again. He was used for a burglary planned by Bill Sikes. Sikes, Oliver and two other men tried to burgle a gorgeous sumptuous house in the country; they needed Oliver because of his tiny figure thanks to which he could get into the house through a window and unlock the door from the inside. Nevertheless, occupants of the house woke up and they shot Oliver, the others managed to escape. Oliver got a place in the house which should have been burgled. He narrated the truth to the occupants of the house – an elderly Mrs. Maylie and her adopted daughter Rose; then they safeguarded him from the police and took charge of him. In the meantime, a few new characters appeared in the story. Monks was one of them. He was also a criminal; he knew the Fagin's gang and he searched for Oliver.

Another new character is a dying old nurse in the workhouse where Oliver was born. On her deathbed she confessed to a theft to Mrs. Corney, the administrator of the workhouse. The nurse robbed Oliver's mother of a medallion belonging to Oliver. Monks redeemed the medallion from Mrs. Corney and he immediately threw it away into the river. Thereafter Nancy accidentally listened to the conversation between Monks and Fagin and from it she realized that Oliver was actually Monks' half-brother and Monks wanted to devastate him because of their father's inheritance. Nancy had twinges of conscience and she encountered Rose whom she told about Monks' plan. However, that right action recoiled on Nancy: Bill Sikes murdered her after he realized she divulged the plan. On the run from the police Sikes died by hanging by mischance. Meanwhile Rose told everything she heard from Nancy to Mr. Brownlow and others. Mr. Brownlow succeeded in capturing Monks and tangled family relationships slowly started to disentangle.

The Role of Legal System

It came to light that Mr. Brownlow was supposed to marry a girl who regrettably died very young. Mr. Brownlow knew also her brother Mr. Leeford who did not get married for love but for coercion. A baby was born to the unhappy family – Monks. Mr. Leeford later split up with his unloved wife and he had another child with another woman – Oliver’s mother. A certain rich relative of Mr. Leeford bequeathed large property to him which should pass to his sons – Monks and Oliver – after Mr. Leeford’s death. The last surprising family relationship was revealed by Rose who was actually a younger sister of Oliver’s mother, so she was Oliver’s aunt. The story has the happy ending. Fagin was arrested and hanged, Monks was also arrested and he died of an illness in prison. Mr. Brownlow adopted Oliver and Rose got married to Mrs. Maylie’s son. They all became a big happy family.

Conclusion

In *Oliver Twist*, Dickens highlights how a lack of education and opportunity traps individuals in a cycle of poverty and crime. At the start of his life, Oliver lives in a small-town workhouse, where he frequently hears older men claim that city life offers ways of survival unknown to those raised in the countryside. The rapid urbanization of the Industrial Revolution deepened the divide between rural and urban living, reinforcing the belief that London provided opportunities for those willing to seek them. However, for destitute children like Oliver, the city often meant life on the streets, where survival depended on assistance or, more often, exploitation. Through this, Dickens critiques the systemic neglect and economic disparity that drive vulnerable individuals toward desperation and criminality.

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